

124; FDMS: 487 ($M+Na$)⁺, 465 ($M+H$)⁺ and 303 (aglycone+H)⁺; pc (Whatman 1, 28°, ascending, $R_f \times 100$) 7(H_2O), 9(15% HOAc), 41 (50% HOAc), 33 (phenol) and 26 (t-BAW); acid hydrolysis yielded bracteatin and D-glucose. It was identified as 6,3',4',5'-tetrahydroxy-4-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-auroone (bractein), earlier reported from *Helichrysum bracteatum*^{1,5}.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Professor Ferdinand Bohlmann, Director, Institute for Organic Chemistry, Technical University of Berlin, West Germany for nmr spectra.

References

1. J. D. HOOKER, "Flora of British India", L. Reeve and Co., Kent, 1954, Vol. III, p. 290.
2. C. E. O. FISHER, "Flora of the Presidency of Madras", Botanical Survey of India, Calcutta, 1957, Vol. III, p. 491.
3. A. H. MERICLI, B. DAMADYAN and B. OUBUKCU, *Sci. Pharm.*, 1986, **54**, 363.
4. B. OUBUKCU and B. DAMADYAN, *Fitoterapia*, 1986, **57**, 124.
5. J. JAKUPOVIC, J. KUHNKE, A. SCHUSTER, M. A. METWALLY and F. BOHLMANN, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, **25**, 1183.
6. J. JAKUPOVIC, V. P. PATHAK, F. BOHLMANN R. M. KING and H. ROBINSON, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 803.
7. J. JAKUPOVIC, T. TERTZ and F. BOHLMANN, *Phytochemistry*, 1987, **26**, 1841.
8. C. J. V. SCHYF, T. G. DEKKER, T. G. FOURIE and F. O. SMYCKERS, *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.*, 1986, **30**, 375.
9. F. SILVA and A. ABRAHAM, *Fitoterapia*, 1981, **52**, 195.
10. T. J. MABRY, K. R. MARKHAM and M. B. THOMAS, "The Systematic Identification of Flavonoids", Springer, New York, 1970.
11. K. R. MARKHAM, "Techniques of Flavonoid Identification", Academic, London, 1982.
12. A. G. R. NAIR, T. R. SETHARAMAN, B. VOIRIN and J. F. BONWIN, *Phytochemistry*, 1986, **25**, 768.
13. S. S. SUBRAMANIAN and A. G. R. NAIR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, **2**, 338.
14. T. A. GRISSMAN and J. B. HARBORNE, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 4622.
15. R. HANSEL, L. LANGHAMMER and A. G. ALBRECHT, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1962, 599.

Chemical Investigation of the Roots of

Flueggea microcarpa Blume

SUJATA KUNDU, M. SAHAI and A. B. RAY*

Department of Medicinal Chemistry, I.M.S.,
Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi-221 005

Manuscript received 16 May 1989, accepted 23 May 1989

FLUEGGEA microcarpa Blume (Euphorbiaceae) is an indigenous medicinal plant distributed throughout India^{1,2} and several publications on the chemical constituents of different parts of this plant have appeared³⁻⁶, the last one coming from Murthy and Jairaj⁷. However, contrary to the claim of the last two authors⁷, the occurrence of bergenin in

this plant was recorded earlier and we reported in our previous communication⁸ the isolation of gallic acid, ellagic acid, quercetin, β -sitosterol glucoside and N₅-methyl-tetrahydro- β -carboline in addition to bergenin, the major constituent of the leaves. The present paper reports the characterisation of a relatively rare plant phenolic, norbergenin (1) and an alkaloid, securinine⁹ isolated from the roots of *F. microcarpa*.

The air-dried and powdered roots of *F. microcarpa* were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and acetone. The concentrated acetone extract on keeping, yielded a solid which was crystallised from methanol to afford colourless prisms, C₁₅H₁₄O₉ (HRMS: M^+ , 314.0637), m.p. 281°; it gave positive phenolic reaction. It showed in its ¹H nmr spectrum (methanol-d₄), 1H singlet at δ 7.07 for a lone aromatic hydrogen and a series of multiplets spread over the region δ 3.2–4.9 for seven hydrogens. While the signal for a single aromatic hydrogen suggested the presence of a pentasubstituted phenyl nucleus, the appearance of signals for only eight out of fourteen hydrogens present in the molecule indicated the probable presence of six exchangeable hydrogens as hydroxyl groups. This assumption was proved to be correct by acetylation of the compound which yielded a hexaacetate (1a), m.p. 212°. The ¹H nmr spectral data of this hexaacetate compared well with those of bergenin pentaacetate with the only difference that the former lacked the aromatic methoxyl signal of the latter and instead showed an extra acetoxymethyl signal. Based on these observations, the isolated compound was considered to be des-O-methylbergenin (norbergenin) which was confirmed from the observation that the trimethyl ether of the isolated compound was identical in all respects with the dimethyl ether of bergenin.

Though preparation of norbergenin⁹ from bergenin was reported in 1936, its natural occurrence was first reported¹⁰ in 1981 and this is the third report of its isolation from a plant. It is interesting to note that while the leaves of *F. microcarpa* are rich in bergenin, its roots yielded only norbergenin.

The acetone extract, left after removal of norbergenin, responded to Dragendorff's reagent for alkaloids and the alkaloid fraction separated by standard procedure, on chromatographic resolution over silica gel yielded a pale yellow solid which crystallised from methanol as cubes, C₁₅H₁₅NO₉ (M^+ , 217) m.p. 145°; [α]_D –1283.33 (CHCl₃). Colour of the alkaloid, its melting point, high negative rotation and above all the perfect matching of its ¹H nmr signals with the reported values⁹ established its identity as securinine. Isolation of securinine from the roots of *F. microcarpa* is of interest in view of the fact that beside flueggine, an uncharacterised alkaloid, the only other alkaloid that was isolated from the leaves of this plant was an indole alkaloid. The occurrence of securinine

in this plant is also significant from chemotaxonomic viewpoint because of its close relationship with *Securinega* species as has been pointed out by some authors¹¹.

Experimental

The plant material was procured from United Chemical and Allied Products, Calcutta. The dried powdered roots (0.8 kg) was defatted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and extracted with acetone. The acetone extract was concentrated to a small volume (150 ml) and left overnight. The resulting solid was crystallised from MeOH to afford colourless prisms of norbergenin, $C_{15}H_{14}O_9$, m.p. 281°; m/z 314.0637 ($C_{15}H_{14}O_9$), 195.0243 ($C_9H_8O_5$) and 194.0201 ($C_9H_8O_5$); 1H nmr (MeOH- d_4) δ 7.07 (1H, s, ArH) and 3.3–4.9 (7H, complex multiplet,

1; R=H
1a; R=Ac

7 carbinyl hydrogens). *Norbergenin hexaacetate* (1a): $C_{21}H_{26}O_{15}$, m.p. 212°; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$) δ 1.99, 2.02, 2.04, 2.23, 2.25, 2.27 (3H, s, each 6-OAc), 3.72 (1H, d, J 8 Hz with fine splitting, H-5'), 4.03 (1H, d with fine splitting, J 11 Hz, H-6'), 4.23 (1H, d, J 11 Hz, H-6'), 4.32 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, H-2'), 4.79 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1'), 5.06 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, H-4') and 5.40 (1H, t, J 8 Hz, H-3'). *Non-bergenin trimethyl ether*: (MeOH + CH_3N_3), m.p. 192°; identical with bergenin dimethyl ether in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., co-tlc). *Securinine*: the mother liquor of norbergenin was freed from solvent, stirred with aqueous citric acid (7%) and filtered. The filtrate was basified with NH_4OH and extracted with EtOAc. The concentrated EtOAc extract on chromatography over silica gel yielded a pale yellow crystalline solid, $C_{15}H_{14}NO_8$ (M^+ , 217), m.p. 145°; $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -1283.33 ($CHCl_3$); ν_{max} ($CHCl_3$) 1 810sh, 1 755, 1 640 cm^{-1} ; 1H nmr ($CDCl_3$) identical with reported values of securinine, m/z 217 (99.9%), 134 (100%), 106 (100%).

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (S.K.) is grateful to Ministry of Health, New Delhi, for financial assistance.

References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYER and I. O. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1956, p. 121.
2. K. R. KIRTIKAR and B. D. BASU, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Vol. 3, Singh and Singh, Dehradun, 1985, p. 2280.

3. S. A. AHMAD, S. K. KAPOOR and A. ZAMER, *Phytochemistry*, 1972, 11, 452.
4. T. K. RAY, D. R. MISRA and H. N. KHASTAGIR, *Phytochemistry*, 1973, 12, 1819.
5. R. A. PARIS, H. MOYSE-MIGNON and J. LEMEN, *Ann. Pharm. Franc.*, 1955, 13, 245.
6. S. KUMAR, M. SAHAI and A. B. RAY, *Planta Medica*, 1985, 466.
7. Y. L. N. MURTHY and M. A. JAIRAJ, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, 65, 788.
8. S. SAITO, K. KOTERA, N. SUGIMOTO, Z. HORII and Y. TAMURA, *Chem. Ind. (London)*, 1962, 1652.
9. A. E. TCHITCHIBABINE, A. V. KIRSANOV and G. A. ARBOUSOV, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Fr.*, 1986, 3, 2843.
10. S. B. KALIDHAR, M. R. PARTHASARTHY and P. SHARMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1981, 20, 720.
11. "The Wealth of India—Raw Materials", C. S. I. R., New Delhi, 1972, Vol. 9, p. 268.

Reactive Disperse Dyes. Synthesis of Sulphonylazido Group Reactive Disperse Dyes and their Application on Nylon and Polyester Fibers

N. M. NAIK and K. R. DESAI*

Department of Chemistry, South Gujarat University, Surat-395 007

Manuscript received 15 February 1988, revised 16 December 1988, accepted 23 May 1989

THE mechanism of the reaction of reactive dyes containing reactive units such as triazinylchloride or vinylsulphone involves nucleophilic substitution or nucleophilic addition¹. As a result, these dyes will react with fibre such as cellulose, wool and nylon which contain nucleophilic groups and will be non-reactive towards polyester and polypropylene which are devoid of nucleophilic groups. Several azo and anthraquinone dyes and fluorescent whiteners containing sulphonylazido group for hydrophobic fibres² and also reactive disperse dyes have been prepared.

Several reactive disperse dyes have been involving nitrene intermediates⁴ containing sulphonyl azido group(s) and involving sulphonylnitrene as the reactive intermediate. Sulphonylazides decompose thermally or photolytically to form sulphonylnitrenes which are readily inserted to various organic bonds including C–H bond⁵. These dyes were then dyed on nylon and polyester fibres by the usual disperse dyeing methods.

In our initial study, we have prepared several reactive disperse dyes containing sulphonyl azido group of the general structure 1 and dyed on nylon and polyester fibres by the usual disperse dyeing methods.